

Use of semantic and business analytics to monitor integrations between enterprise applications in IT

J. A. Blanco García¹, F. de J. Pozos-Texon²

¹Universidad Cristbal Coln, Boca del Ro, Veracruz México

¹jimmy1087@gmail.com

²Universidad Cristbal Coln, Boca del Ro, Veracruz México

²fpozost@ucc.mx

Área de participación: *Sistemas Computacionales*

Resumen

El artículo plantea un modelo para monitorear interfaces e incrementar la calidad en el servicio en las integraciones empresariales en la industria de la manufactura. Siguiendo los lineamientos de “business analytics” se construye un modelo descriptivo, recuperando información a partir del “meta-data” y de las entidades de negocios que maneja cada interfaz. Encima de esta capa, un análisis semántico resuelve el contexto de los problemas, en donde se evalúa la severidad y la cantidad de ocurrencias en un periodo de tiempo, se determina también, si se debe notificar a expertos para que tomen acciones y aceleren las soluciones. La contribución principal de este modelo reside en habilitar una plataforma que permite a los especialistas automatizar el análisis de los incidentes en las integraciones conectadas a una aplicación central, por ejemplo, un “Manufacturing Execution System” (MES). De manera particular busca mejorar, mediante la automatización de notificaciones, la calidad en el servicio.

Palabras clave: *integración, análisis, semántico, ontología*

Abstract

This paper presents a model to track interface activities in order to increase the Quality of Service (QoS) delivered by integrations between enterprise applications in the manufacturing industry. Following the guidelines of business analytics, a descriptive model is built over an ontology, which assembles meaning from meta-data and business entities that are conveyed in each interface. On top of that, a semantic analysis breaks down the context of issues, evaluating the severity and the number of occurrences of the problem in a timespan, it also notifies experts when needed to galvanize actions and expedite solutions. The main contribution of this model relies on building a framework that enables knowledgeable workers to engineer analysis of issues occurring in integrations that are connected to a central application such as a Manufacturing Execution System (MES). The principal claim is that by automating smart notifications and decisions, the QoS can improve.

Key words: *integration, semantic, analytics, ontology*

Introduction

One of the complex challenges that enterprises in the manufacturing industry face, especially those that are large and dynamic, befalls in the integration of information across internal systems. Each application that constitutes the enterprise system specializes in solving particular needs of the business, in mentioning a couple; an Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) handles the resources, while a Manufacturing Execution System (MES) manages the manufacturing process, and so the Customer Relationship Management (CRM) controls the customer relationship. Individually, each program is an expert in its field, yet, to operate correctly, they depend on having suitable information, which most times than not, comes from interacting with other applications.

It is with each link well founded among applications that dependency grows, not only on the technical aspect, but also very often on the functional side. Users from different departments expect information to be at one's disposal, which sets a high expectation on systems to work together seamlessly, which in turn bequeaths integration as a highly sensitive subject inside enterprises.

Within the integration layer, utilities in middlewares can trace messages across endpoints, yet, the reports that these programs produce befalls on the technical viewpoint, conveying the success or failure, of delivering the message solely. This article moves on to the next frontier that is to be conquest by the integration layer, the use of semantic analytics to ease the tracking of messages. By identifying the intention and key elements within the content of the message, the qualitative analysis is improved. Instead of informing failure rates, as stated by [1], the qualitative layer provides insights to the support team about real business problems.

After all, the difficulty of problems in integration and the quandary pertains to the fact that interfaces are built upon business requirements, which are highly dynamic, as described by [2] when referring to enterprise applications characteristics. This entails a hard rhythm to follow in the development and cycle support. Thus, in the light of easing of the hassle of various adaptations that interfaces go through; alterations to business rules, contracts, volume, among other changes. There is a clear opportunity for analytical tools to come into stage and relief stress and time required from the development and support team. Bringing semantic information and context to issues can render valuable qualitative reports in the assistance of classification, prioritization, trending analysis, and identification of error patterns as claimed by [1].

Altogether, in the manufacturing industry, interfaces are central to operations. Moreover, the reputation of the Information Technology (IT) department is highly attached to how well systems work together as a whole. Even though there are contracts and quantitative metrics, such as Service Level Agreements (SLA) that can measure up the Quality of Service (QoS) among enterprise applications, trust, is challenging to measure. As outlined by [3], trustworthy is an abstract concept built on specific beliefs and assumptions about how services keep up with expectations. In this paper, the viewpoint adopted to measure the QoS delivered by interfaces, stems from measuring how well they keep up with changes through time as the business does. Consequently, semantic and analytical tools bring forth valuable business information in the form of context, which can be used to expedite solutions, to monitor the QoS, and to track issues.

Even though the problem has been introduced, it is essential to exhibit research underpinning the model's operation. For these, the following three sections expose concepts published in papers within the integration ecosystem in the manufacturing industry. First, a hierarchy model serves as a frame to position systems within levels of automation; it is presented jointly with concepts useful for this paper, suchlike the definition of an interface, and its classifications according to Izza [5]. After that, comparable semantic tools are mentioned. Finally, certain notions from the business analytics domain are described, which outlines the knowledge generated by the model.

Automation levels

The American National Standards Institute (ANSI) and the International Society of Automation (ISA) establish the ANSI standard ISA-95, which is now a reference in the automation of enterprises in the manufacturing industry. In Figure 1, Southekal [4] depicts the hierarchy model of information that systems abide at different levels of execution; it conveys the responsibilities that each application has within the manufacturing context.

Figure 1. "Systems as organized by ANSI/ISA-95" by Southekal [4]

What is lightly infer from the diagram above is that data stems from lower levels at different rates. In each level, information is assemble from various applications by forging bonds. Overall, these relationships entails complex scenarios of dependency. As interfaces habitually suffer alterations and connections have to keep up with the dynamism prevailing in enterprise applications, a characteristic described by [2], wherein, workflows and business scenarios frequently adapt to look toward the business exigency.

Although the model could monitor interfaces at all levels, this paper focuses on tracking integration problems at levels three and four in the hierarchy level, since the information has a broader scope in terms of process and the business most times than not can tolerate a more significant time to analyze issues.

Integration

As claimed by Izza [5], the definition of integration found in the dictionary comes from the act of integrating, with an etymology "integrare," which means "making a whole"; joining a vaster set. In accordance to that baseline, integration is the act of bringing together components to form a complete whole, granting along the way, properties to the action, which is the subject discussed in this paper.

Interfaces can be analyzed from different perspectives. From the dimensions point of view according to [5], the syntax encompasses the contracts of services. An example in this category is the Web Service Description Language (WSDL), which is an Extensible Markup Language (XML) that describes Simple Object Access Protocol (SOAP) messages. It can be used to describe the context of services upon the schema structure, the business entities, and from the signatures of related services.

The next dimension to analyze in the opinion of [5] is the semantic layer, whose primary aim is to identify the intention of messages. One proposal in this category stems from the standard Universal Description, Discovery and Integration protocol (UDDI), an XML-based registry that fosters primarily for service discoverability, interoperability, and interchangeability, which allows services to be exchanged as needed on the fly. Habitually the UDDI is also used along with SOAP messages within enterprises, which remains the chosen architecture in the context of enterprise application, as its more ubiquitous adoption on the internet fell off in favor of the Representative State Transfer (REST) architecture style.

With those two layers described, the model would be able to check compliance of contracts and to organize messages into categories. Yet, the functional priorities, dependencies between services and actions, which are defined by knowledgeable workers, would be hard to model and describe in a syntax (WSDL) or semantic language (UDDI). Therefore, the model uses a Resource Description Framework (RDF) document to describe the meaning of each interface, similar to what the following two initiatives do in the field of the semantic web according to [5].

First, the Web Ontology Language – Semantic (OWL-S) [6] is a collaborative effort by BBN Technologies and some other enterprises and universities to define an upper-ontology for a semantic mark-up of services. It semantically describes the capabilities and properties of web services using Web Ontology Language – Description Logic (OWL-DL) language, also known as OWL-2 [7].

On top of the OWL-S, the Web Service Modeling Ontology (WSMO) [8] uses a Web Service Modeling Language (WSML) to provide a formal syntax to semantics. It is built upon four different components: ontologies (which are formal entities), web services, goals (which define the intention to be executed by the web service publisher), and mediator (that address the technical or functional issues that may arise in the integration).

Regardless of these two initiatives, Izza [5] claim that the semantic layer does not adequately address the issue of service description and that the UDDI registries fell short when describing behavior. The shortfall is reinforced by [9], who points out that this occurs even with the support of standard taxonomies such as the North American Industry Classification System (NAICS), or the United Nations Standard Products and Services Code (UN/SPCS), or the International Organization for Standardization ISO 3166.

Business Analytics

For solving particular problems at the semantic level, the model frames the knowledge of each interface under the business analytics layers, which will be briefly described in the following paragraphs.

The definition of Business Analytics taken from [10], states that "is a process that transforms data into actions through analysis and insights in the context of organizational decision making and problem-solving." [11] Divide it into three groups: descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive. The most widely used is the descriptive one, which categorizes, classifies, and consolidates data into meaningful information, habitually presenting the results in charts and reports. The predictive analytics examines historical data and looks for patterns and relationships, to predict future consequences and risks. Lastly, prescriptive analytics is primarily used as a means to identify the best alternatives when minimizing or maximizing goals. It is commonly used with optimization techniques in simulations to understand choices and consequences.

In the model, when a message is analyzed under the viewpoint of a descriptive layer, entities are outlined, and dependencies can be understood. With these service contracts, context can be built, ensuring a better analysis when errors occur. As stated by Evans [11], the descriptive layer can enable context for a knowledge worker to galvanize action into solution. Also, it is possible to engineer the workflow of future responses, for example, if a known operation pattern has an alert, the intelligent analysis of the problem directs the right response alternatives to the available expert to prioritize and execute the corrective action.

Both, the descriptive and predictive layer benefits the model objective. By joining the semantic analysis with the analytical reports, critical areas of integration can be detected, bottlenecks and errors can be addressed in order to reduce impacts of subsequent problems that may arise if they are not heeded.

Methodology

The literature review so far settles the underpinnings of the model. Hereafter, this section describes how the model works, how it tracks interfaces while Enterprise Applications communicate and establish bonds between them. Next comes a diagram of entities and activities that elucidates the approach taken in the model to improve the meaning of integrations among enterprise applications. Thereafter the model is described to crystallize further the benefits that can derive from its implementation.

Integration Monitor Model

Although not explicitly mentioned so far, the improvement in the degree of confidence in information is the ultimate goal pursued by this paper. Business analytics can crystallize errors that impinge the quality of the information received and transmitted within integrations in industrial systems. Evans [11], states some of the challenges that interfaces endure. Each point has a counter-annotation stating how the model makes sense of the problem.

- Networks cannot guarantee message delivery; hence, a fault tolerance configuration can evaluate the status of the message to keep up with operations, even when the information is not fully complete.
- Asynchronous messages can get lost. It is essential to detect missing information in order to galvanize actions from knowledgeable workers.
- Data-centric messages can be processed in disorder due to the order of arrival in the reception queue or due to a network delay, from here, when errors occur, analytic tools provide context to establish the order of events and the relationships involved.
- Receiving systems process messages incorrectly affecting the business workflow. Either by executing erroneous rules or by technical mistakes, identification, and classification is vital to expedite solutions.

Integration scenarios are far from simple and the lack of context affects the time for resolution. Habitually, when errors appear in interfaces, they get pushed on to the support team, for analysis, categorization, and ultimately for reaching solutions. However, if at least one of the problems is complex, it will demand more attention from pundits, which is time-consuming. Moreover, depending on the quality of data exchanged between the systems, nuisances can be tangled with urgencies, and more often than not, all issues can quickly become turmoil for everyone.

The model provides a framework to measure the quality of data exchanged, and provide means to act upon precepts. Figure 2 depicts the components that constitutes the model. Further sections describes its functionality.

Figure 2. Architecture of the integration monitor model.

1. Descriptive layer

The WSDL delineates the signature of a message in terms of data types, lengths, and formats. However, it is not enough to define meaning. To solve this, the model builds an ontology constituted primarily by a hierarchy of entities with links to other services, plus a dictionary of the meta-data of each event. The ontology follows the guidelines from the W3C [7] to represent knowledge: using Entities as business objects along with categories to classify interfaces in the Service Profile layer. To validate the structure of the conceptual model, a verifier tool such as the Ontology Pitfall Scanner (OOPS) evaluates that the ontology complies with the syntax.

As an example, the message depicted in Figure 3, refers to a work order request, a standard interface between an ERP and a MES system. The left column portrays the message in an XML format. The middle column is express in OWL 2 terms, it is deconstructed in a diagram of entities, and it depicts a semantic description of the same message. Last, in the right column, relevant attributes that will be handled in the context of the message are displayed, they are useful to the Service Manager to augment the semantic information.

Figure 3. Model representations of an archetype message.

In summary, the descriptive layer sets the foundation for the model. It is the same as the one that the business analytics proclaims should be obtained first to gain further control. The ontology is stored in documents following the Resource Description Format (RDF) defined by the W3C [12]. This way, each interface gets a document delineating what the business considers relevant in terms of priorities and the relationships with other interfaces.

2. Decision layer

The second level of the model builds a context on top of the entities defined in the ontology. The primary goal of this layer is to engineer the decisions taken by pundits in the past. As stated by Daff [1], the knowledgeable worker engineers a response to each abnormal event before a series of costly abnormal cascades into significant losses of capability, capacity and margin per unit. Thereby, the entities model in this layer, capture the meta-rules that will allow an expert in the business to take actions regarding each interface.

3. Knowledgeable layer

This layer yield insights about key indicators of behavior of every connection, which is relevant to the perception of quality. At this stage, patterns are the foundation of predictive models, they can be used to infer trends and in taking preventive action. Historical data can help build up cases that attract adequate attention instead of just having the team running out to solve apparent-urgent issues, which may turn out to be non-important ones.

To better illustrate the workflow of analysis that the integration monitor executes, Figure 4 depicts an UML diagram.

Figure 4. Activity diagram of a message analyzed by the Integration Monitor

The workflow begins immediately after a message is received or is sent to another system. First, the Context manager calls the extractor component to parse the message according to the entities defined in the Ontology, along with the meta-data. The second stage comes in place when the service manager sorts out the message and fills up the relevant information to complement the service profile, gathering additional data from other sources.

The third phase is carried out by the Context Manager, which uses the key elements of the message to find out if the message matches some error conditions already specified in the catalog of scenarios. When a match occurs, the manager proceeds to evaluate what actions to take and whom to notify. The criticality of the notification is defined by two conditions; the priority established in the service profile and the result of applying a time-frequency analysis that the context manager executes.

This analysis evaluates the number of events occurring in a certain period. First, it obtains a time-frequency distribution regarding the normal parameters of the behavior in the interface. Then the number of current errors is evaluated against the lower and upper limits in the function. The instant an error surpasses the standard behavior expected from the service, a snapshot gets build, which is part of the context that is conveyed in the notification to experts. The context includes; the dependencies, the impact that the interface has with other components, the registry of events occurred in a timespan, and the suggested actions to be taken, plus the meta-data detailing the number of errors accumulated over this period. The main reason for having this information frozen is that the context may change in time.

Thereafter, in stage six and seven, the analytic manager, uses historic data to evaluate trends and bottlenecks. This component is in charge of presenting a qualitative summary of the interface behavior. Its main job is to update the key performance indicators defined in the Service Level Agreement of each interface. Moreover, this component can make inquiries and relate events from different interfaces in order to display correlations. It is up to the analyst to use this module capability to evaluate complex scenarios with particular circumstances.

As it can be seen, the entities gathered at the beginning of the workflow, set the basis of the models operation. Each level aggregates the previous one, and it is in this way that knowledge is generated. This model relies on the list of scenarios gathered and engineered, they are used for detection of similar errors, in favor of suggesting actions that can lead to quicker solutions. The model can start tracking interfaces with a base list of scenarios defined in the ontology. However, to improve the QoS that each interface delivers, every time new errors appear, they need to be fed into the model. It is similar to what testing models endure, the more key scenarios defined and automated, the better the framework can assure quality.

Results and discussions

The verification of the model is the next stage for this paper. In order to prove that the QoS in integrations between enterprise applications can improve when messages get tracked, a prototype must be placed in a central system in order to generate enough statistics about the interfaces that it process. The minimum key indicators that prove the rate of success that the model has are:

- The reduction in the average time that it takes to solve problems by an interface.
- The increase in the rate of messages tracked divided by the number of messages received and sent.
- The number of scenarios tracked by each interface.
- The number of errors tracked and solved, divided by the number of errors untracked and solved.
- A qualitative survey from analysts that supports integrations.

Future research

The model tracks integrations surrounding one central system. However, future work may evaluate the tracking of all integrations occurring in all applications inside an enterprise, which presents an exciting challenge for scaling the model. Especially because the model gathers information from business entities to build semantic context.

Conclusions

It is reasonable to speak of a daunting number of scenarios when describing integrations. Interfaces are quite diverse, and each one has specific intricacies. They can easily surpass the capacity of the support team, especially when problems lack context. Thus, this paper presents a model to ease the tracking of activity in interfaces.

For these reasons, the model has been designed to aid in the complex task of assessment that interfaces require when errors occur. The better context that can be built the more likelihood there is in having the problem solved as fast as possible without draining the team's attention. It is well known that analysts repeat the same actions when evaluating problems, and it is precisely in this spot that the model takes its merit. As described above, it provides a framework for business analysts and IT developers, to engineer workflows and expedites solutions. The model emphasizes on extracting essential information along with business data in order to expedite notifications to knowledgeable workers, but it also propose to take advantage of historical data and lessons learned from the past to automate the workflow of information that has been involved in previous solutions.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my deep gratitude to Dr. Felipe de Jesús Pozos Texon my research supervisor, for his enthusiastic encouragement and useful critiques of this research work.

References

- [1] C. Gifford and D. Daff, "Factory Automation: ISA-95 evolves to support smart manufacturing and IIoT.," 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.isa.org/intech/20171203/>. [Accessed 31 July 2019].
- [2] M. Singh and M. Huhns, M. Service-oriented computing: semantics, processes, agents, J. Wiley, 2005.
- [3] M. Tang, X. Dai, J. Liu and J. Chen, "Towards a trust evaluation middleware for cloud service selection," *Future Generation Computer Systems*, no. 74, pp. 302-312, 2017.
- [4] P. H. Southehal, Data for Business Performance: The Goal-Question-Metric (GQM) Model to Transform Business Data into an Enterprise Asset, Technics Publications, 2017.
- [5] S. Izza, "Integration of industrial information systems: from syntactic to semantic integration approaches," *Enterprise Information Systems*, no. 3, pp. 1-57, 2009.
- [6] Martin, D. et. al, "OWL-S: Semantic Markup for Web Services," 22 November 2004. [Online]. Available: <https://www.w3.org/Submission/OWL-S/>. [Accessed 31 July 2019].
- [7] Hitzler P. et al., "OWL 2 Web Ontology Language Primer (Second Edition)," W3C Recommendation, 11 December 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://www.w3.org/TR/2012/REC-owl2-primer-20121211/>. [Accessed 01 August 2019].
- [8] Bruijn J. et al., "Web Service Modeling Ontology (WSMO)," 3 June 2005. [Online]. Available: <https://www.w3.org/Submission/WSMO/>. [Accessed 01 August 2019].
- [9] Dogac, A. et al., "Semantically enriched web services for the travel industry," *ACM SIGMOD Record*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 21-27, 2004.
- [10] M. J. Liberatore and L. Wenhong, "The analytics movement: Implications for operations research.," *INFORMS Journal on Applied Analytics*, vol. 40, no. 4, pp. 313-324, 2010.
- [11] J. R. Evans and C. H. Lidner, "Business Analytics: The Next Frontier for Decision Sciences," 2012. [Online]. Available: http://www.cbpp.uaa.alaska.edu/afef/business_analytics.htm. [Accessed 01 August 2019].
- [12] A. Zimmermann, "RDF 1.1: On Semantics of RDF Datasets," 25 February 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://www.w3.org/TR/2014/NOTE-rdf11-datasets-20140225/>. [Accessed 01 August 2019].